

Effects of Particle Exit Diameter on the Performance of a Gas-Solid Cyclone Separator of High Solid Loading Designed for a Circulating Fluidized Adsorption Refrigeration System

Modupe Atinuke Oluleye

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering,
Ekiti State University, PMB 5363, Ekiti State, Nigeria

Rabah Boukhanouf

Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham,
NG7 2RD Nottingham, United Kingdom

Suggested Citation

Oluleye, M.A., & Boukhanouf, R. (2024). Effects of Particle Exit Diameter on the Performance of a Gas-Solid Cyclone Separator of High Solid Loading Designed for a Circulating Fluidized Adsorption Refrigeration System. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 524-535. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).45](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).45)

Abstract:

In applications such as in chemical, pharmaceutical, nanotechnology and food industries where cyclones are used for product separation and recovery, the gases carry a product rather than a waste in which the solid loadings (C_o) can be much higher. Ensuring efficient products separation and recovery from the air stream without damaging their characteristics becomes so crucial. It is therefore highly imperative to consider the effects of the particle (product) exit design on the cyclone performance for optimization purposes. The effects of particle exit diameter (d_{pe}) on the performance of a reverse flow tangential gas-solid cyclone separator designed for application in a circulating fluidised adsorption refrigeration (CFAR)

system have been numerically investigated. Activated carbon of 50–500 μm particle size range with C_o range of 5-30 kg solid/kg of gas at the gas inlet velocity (V_i) of 10m/s was used. The simulation results showed a decreasing trend in the pressure drop (ΔP) and an increasing trend in the cut size diameter (x_{50}) with increasing d_{pe} for all C_o . There was no observable change in the overall separation efficiency with increasing d_{pe} over the tested range of C_o but a slight variation was observed with particles sizes below this size range.

Keywords: Gas–solid cyclone separator, Collection efficiency, Pressure drop, High solid loading, Adsorption, Activated carbon.

Introduction

A cyclone separator is a widespread device used in many industrial areas and daily life for removing fine particulate matter from a gas stream. This separator has been used for more than 100 years due to its simple and robust design, but was continuously further developed and adapted to specific applications. The mostly

used configuration is the reverse flow type cyclone exhibiting however, a very complex vortex flow with high turbulence (Sommerfeld & Taborda, 2024). A reverse flow tangential gas-solid cyclone separator is defined as a device that uses vortex cyclonic separation mechanism to separate particulate solids from a gas stream by an induced centrifugal force which is tangentially

imparted on the cyclone cylinder wall. This force coupled with the density gradient between the fluid and the solid particles, increases the relative settling velocity of the solid particles and thereby driving them towards the wall of the cyclone where they slide to the particle exit and are thereby collected.

The following benefits offered by cyclone have favored its extensive applications (among which are: sampling, agricultural cleaning, industrial processes, environmental control, separation and removal of solid particles from carrier fluids or process gases): simple design, low capital cost, low maintenance requirements and absence of wear as there are no moving parts, relatively small space requirement, relative power economy, flexibility for use in extreme operating conditions because they can be made from a variety of refractory and high corrosion-resistant materials for special purposes. According to (U. Muschelknautz, 2019), cyclone can be used in processes requiring high temperatures, high pressures and high solids loads for example, 30 kg solids per kg gas, and finally, they allow the reuse of the separated particles.

Gas-solid cyclone separator has always found its relevance in applications that involve the removal of particulate solids from gas streams since the middle of the 19th century. Large recirculation cyclones with high concentrations of particulate solids have gained considerable importance in the field of circulating fluidized bed (CFB) technology (Trefz & Muschelknautz, 1993). For instance, according to (E Muschelknautz & Greif) and (Grace, Avidan, & Knowlton, 1997), cyclones have been installed in a coal-burning power plant that uses a CFB system for the purpose of separating solids (comprising $\approx 90\%$ fly ash of 5-500 μm particle size, $\approx 5\text{-}10\%$ partly burned coal of nearly the same size but with lower density, and only $\approx 1\%$ very fine lime particles of 1-15 μm) from exhaust gases and then later circulate them back to the combustor with maximum possible efficiency.

The cases of cyclone applications with high solid or dust loading had long been the focus of many studies. (Zenz, 1975) and (Tawari & Zenz, 1984)

in their study to evaluate cyclone efficiencies from the stream compositions in industrial fluid-bed reactors, observed an increase (notable for particles of smaller sizes) in the collection efficiency of their cyclone for higher solid loadings in the range of 0.001868-1.868 kg solid/kg of gas.

The results of the tests conducted by (Tuzla & Chen, 1992) to investigate the influence of solid loadings on the performance of a 0.406 m diameter cyclone separator operating in a CFB showed that, for a gas entrance velocity of 3.6 m/s and a loading range of 1.4-5.6 kg of solids/kg of gas, a reduction in collection efficiency (which was notable for smaller particles) was observed for increasing loading.

The effects of solid loading, gas inlet and outlet dimensions on the performance of four industrial scale cyclones of 0.45m diameter were investigated by (Hoffmann, van Santen, Allen, & Clift, 1992). The results of the experiments which were performed under ambient conditions and at an inlet velocity of 15 m/s over a loading range of 0.5–130 g solid per m^3 air showed that an increase in solid loading yielded a reduction in the pressure drop and an increase in the cyclone collection efficiency.

For a particle loading range of $0.3163 \times 10^{-3} - 41 \times 10^{-3}$ kg of solid/kg of gas, (Scheid & Massarani, 1992) did not notice any effect on the collection efficiency of their cyclone.

Up till 0.816 kg of solids/kg of gas, (Tardin Jr. & Goldstein Jr., Brasil, June, 1994, pp. 179–183, in Portuguese.) did not notice any change in the collection efficiency of their cyclone whose primary use was in a CFB. However, for 484 and 807 μm particle sizes, a slight increase in the efficiency was observed between 1.633 and 6.531 kg of solids/kg of gas but there was no observable effect for 356 μm particles.

(Fassani & Goldstein, 2000) experimentally tested the influence of high solid loadings on the separation efficiency and the pressure drop of a cyclone used to separate FCC (Fluid catalytic cracking) catalyst of an extended range of loadings up to 20 kg of solids/kg of gas with

average inlet velocities of 7, 18 and 27 m/s. In the range of concentrations tested, the study results showed that the pressure drop resulting from the flow of the particles-laden air was approximately 47% of that from clean air and that there was increasing separation efficiency with increasing concentration up to 12 kg of solids/kg of gas above which, the efficiency decreased. The results also had it that, the collection efficiency was higher for the inlet velocity of 18 m/s than for 27 m/s at the test conditions.

(Gil, Romeo, & Cortes, 2002) conducted a research by using a scaled-down cold-flow model to study the influences of solid loading on the performance of a novel cyclone which was primarily designed for use in hot-gas cleaning applications (such as in pressurized fluidized bed combustors (PFBC)) with pneumatic extraction of solids. The results of the experiments which were conducted at test conditions: entrance gas velocity range of 9-14 m/s, 30-230 g/kg gas inlet solid loadings range and bottom gas extraction percentages range of 0.3-1.5% had it that, the overall cyclone collection efficiency was enhanced at higher inlet solid concentrations while an increase (for particles less than 10 μm) in fractional efficiency curves was also detected. It was therefore concluded that the two observed effects are indicators of the possibility of increasing collection efficiency by promoting particle agglomeration and spontaneous segregation of solids from the gas stream at cyclone inlet.

(Huang, Ito, Fukasawa, Fukui, & Kuo, 2018) conducted a study to investigate the influence of solid mass loading of 1.6-115.3 g/m³ range on the performances of a cyclone by 2-way coupling CFD simulation and experiments. The experimental results showed that with an entrance gas velocity as low as 15 m/s, there was an improvement in the separation efficiency with increasing particle mass loading. It was then concluded that the cyclone separation efficiency at different solid mass loadings can be reasonably predicted by the CFD simulation.

The experimental results of a study conducted by (Morin, Raynal, Karri, & Cocco, 2021) on the

effect of solid loading (normalized solid loading from 0.014 to 0.41) and inlet aspect ratio (from 3 to 7, keeping the inlet area constant) on the performances of a circulating fluidized bed process (CFB) cyclone which operates at ambient temperature, atmospheric pressure, with air and Geldart Group A glass bead particles of medium diameter of 42.2 μm showed that cyclone pressure drop is primarily affected by solid loading. According to the study, the cyclone pressure drop first decreased for normalized loadings up to about 0.127 before increasing for higher values while the global solid efficiency increased with solid loadings and was also strongly favored by increasing the inlet aspect ratio.

(Yao et al., 2024) numerically investigated the effects of the inlet particle spatial distribution on the performance and flow pattern of a gas-solid cyclone separator of high solid loading with cases of various rectangular inlet particle flow areas using a four-way coupling method. The study results showed that: reduction in the inlet particle flow area would effectively improve the separation efficiency and that a lower inlet particle position would also lead to a better separation performance. The numerical results also had it that, the cyclone performance is more sensitive to the vertical particle distribution than the horizontal.

In this paper, a numerical simulation has been performed to investigate the influence of the particle exit diameter on the performance criteria of a typical reverse flow tangential gas-solid cyclone separator which was designed for application in a circulating fluidised adsorption refrigeration (CFAR) system for the purpose of separating solid desiccant (activated carbon) particles from a carrier gas (air).

Research Gap and Contribution

The design of general-purpose cyclone technology for many process industries is well developed. These industries are often of high-energy consumption intensity and the cyclone requires high energy due to pressure drop, especially at high flow rates. In addition, many

studies focus on either mono-sized particles or a limited range of particle sizes. In this work, the application concerns efficient alternative cooling technology where a balance between solid desiccant particles separation efficiency and low energy consumption remains a challenge, hence there is a need for developing a specific design of a cyclone where the effect of solid particles exit diameter on the overall cyclone performance is investigated.

Furthermore, research efforts have been exhaustively focused on the investigation of the influences of solid loading and other parameters on cyclone performance, particularly on the collection efficiency and the pressure drop of cyclone applications that involve removing a waste product (dust) from a gas but with less attention given to the particle exit design. However, in applications where the gases are carrying a product rather than a waste product, the solid loadings can be much higher. Such applications are found in chemical industries, pharmaceutical industries, nanotechnology, food processing industries and circulating fluidised technologies etc. where cyclones are used for product separation and recovery. In such applications, ensuring efficient products separation and recovery from the air stream without damaging the products quality and characteristics becomes so crucial. It is therefore imperative to focus on the design of that part of cyclone from which the products are collected by considering the effects of the particle (product) exit diameter on the cyclone performance for optimization purposes. Such is the motivation behind this work. The contribution of this paper is aimed to be a guide to carrier gas-product cyclone design Engineers for optimization purposes.

Mathematical Formulation and Computer Modeling

Many methods and models to estimate the performance indicators of gas-solid cyclones are reported in literature. Of practical relevance is

the Muschelknautz method (MM) which is distinguished by its accuracy and reliability in modeling a tangential inlet reverse-flow gas-solid cyclone separator (Hoffmann & Stein, 2008).

For the purpose of optimizing the design of the cyclone in this work, the optimal cyclone geometrical ratios which was determined based on the MM model (E. Muschelknautz & Krambrock, 1970) by (Elsayed & Lacor, 2010) and was reported to have a collection efficiency equal to that of (Stairmand, 1949) cyclone, but with approximately half the pressure drop, was employed with a little modification to S and d_{pe} as shown in Table 1. The cyclone diameter was carefully chosen based on the fixed inlet velocity and the standard design correlation data.

The reverse flow cyclone, which is a typical gas-solid adsorbent cyclone separator designed for use in a circulating fluidized adsorption refrigeration (CFAR) system, is schematically represented in Figure 1. These cyclone dimensions coupled with the parameters given in Table 2 are the baseline parameters for simulating the cyclone using MATLAB software. Activated carbon solid adsorbent particles whose feed size distribution is presented in Figure 2 was used as the particles in the model.

Table 1. Cyclone Geometry and Dimensions

$d = 0.1\text{m}$

Parameter	Dimension	Ratio
Cyclone diameter	d	d
Cyclone inlet height	a	$0.62d$
Cyclone inlet width/ diameter	b	$0.24d$
Vortex finder diameter	d_v	$0.62d$
Cyclone total height	H_t	$4.24d$
Cylinder height	h_{cyl}	$1.62d$
Cone height	h_{con}	$2.62d$
Vortex finder height inside the cyclone	S	S $= a + \frac{d}{8}$
Particle exit diameter	d_{pe}	$0.30d$ - $0.50d$
Vortex finder height outside the cyclone	L_o	$1.62d$

Figure 1. Schematic Representation of the Cyclone Separator

The design of a cyclone for particulate separation from a gas stream requires a careful selection and specification of its geometry, and other operating parameters such as inlet velocity, particle properties, and pressure drop. The main design challenge is to achieve an optimal balance between high separation efficiency and low energy consumption.

Table 2. Physical Properties

S/N	Parameters	Values
1	c_o	5 - 30 kg/kg
2	V_i	10 m/s
3	ρ_g	1.2 kg/m ³
4	\dot{Q}	0.0149 m ³ /s
5	ρ_p	370 kg/m ³
6	ϵ	0.046×10^{-3} m
7	μ_g	1.8×10^{-5} Pa s
8	m	2
9	n	10

Figure 2. Solid Adsorbent Feed Size Distribution

The pressure drop through the cyclone directly affects its energy consumption. It is the effect of frictional losses within the cyclone walls or the separation zone, ΔP_{wall} and the irreversible local losses within the vortex core due to contraction, ΔP_x , (Hoffmann & Stein, 2008). In this analysis, the MM model is selected to analyse the pressure drop (Δp) of the cyclone. Hence, the overall pressure loss within the cyclone can be written as:

$$\Delta P = \Delta P_{wall} + \Delta P_x \quad (1)$$

Where

$$\Delta P_{wall} = f \frac{A_R}{0.9\dot{Q}} \frac{\rho_g}{2} (u_c u_x)^{1.5} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta P_x = \left[2 + 3 \left(\frac{u_x}{v_x} \right)^{1.33} + \left(\frac{u_x}{v_x} \right)^2 \right] \frac{\rho_g}{2} v_x^2 \quad (3)$$

The separation characteristics of a cyclone are best described by using the grade-efficiency curve (GEC), which is the separation efficiency for a given feed particle size or a narrow range of particles size (Hoffmann & Stein, 2008)

The overall efficiency, η_t , is the summation of the efficiency due to saltation in the inlet and that due to classification in the inner vortex. This implies that a proportion of the incoming adsorbent solids that is not captured in the outer vortex is thereby collected through the inner one. Using the MM model however, will require to determine the mass loading effect (saltation), because the amount of solid adsorbents (limiting loading, c_{oL}) the gas can carry in turbulent suspension upon entering the cyclone depends on the median particle size of the feed (x_{median}), the cut-point diameter (x_{50}), and the inlet loading (c_o). This is expressed as:

$$\eta_t = \left(1 - \frac{c_{oL}}{c_o}\right) + \left(\frac{c_{oL}}{c_o}\right) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{W_i}{1 + \left(\frac{x_{50}}{x_i}\right)^m} \quad (4)$$

Where $c_o > c_{oL}$ which satisfies the condition of saltation (mass loading)

$$c_{oL} = 0.025 \left(\frac{x_{50}}{x_{median}}\right) (10 c_o)^{0.15} \quad \text{for } c_o \geq 0.1 \quad \text{and}$$

$$c_{oL} = 0.025 \left(\frac{x_{50}}{x_{median}}\right) (10 c_o)^k \quad \text{for } c_o < 0.1$$

With the exponent, k , given as: $k = -0.11 - 0.10 \ln c_o$ and the cut size diameter of the solid adsorbent x_{50} expressed as:

$$x_{50} = \sqrt{\frac{18\mu_g(0.9\dot{Q})}{2\pi(\rho_p - \rho_g)u_x^2(H_t - S)}} \quad \text{for } Re_p < \sim 0.5$$

(particle settling in the Stokes' law regime) and,

$$x_{50} = 5.18 \frac{\mu_g^{0.375} \rho_g^{0.25} u_{t50}^{0.875}}{\left[\frac{(\rho_p - \rho_g)u_x^2}{r_v}\right]^{0.625}} \quad \text{for } 0.5 < Re_p < 1000 \quad (\text{Stokes' law not holding})$$

$$\text{With } Re_p = \frac{\rho_g u_{t50} x_{50}}{\mu_g} \quad \text{and} \quad u_{t50} = \frac{\dot{Q}}{2\pi r_v (H_t - S)}$$

However, when $c_o < c_{oL}$, that is, the saltation condition is not satisfied, for example in case of: low solid adsorbent loadings, c_o , a fine feed particle size distribution (small x_{median}) and a large x_{50} , the efficiency is expressed by a simplified relationship:

$$\eta_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{W_i}{1 + \left(\frac{x_{50}}{x_i}\right)^m} \quad (5)$$

The solid mass loading, c_o entering the cyclone inlet is given as the ratio of the mass of the solid adsorbent fed into the cyclone to the mass of gas flow entering the cyclone ($c_o = \frac{m_{Sf}}{m_g}$). Therefore, the total mass of solid adsorbent collected from the cyclone particle exit is expressed as follows:

$$m_c = \eta_t m_{Sf} \quad (6)$$

The separation process of the solid adsorbent particles is achieved through the motive power supplied by the centrifugal fan, which is determined by the following:

$$P_f = \dot{Q} \times \Delta P \quad (7)$$

The investigation into the effects of the cyclone particle exit diameter on its performance criteria was studied by varying the d_{pe} from 0.30d to 0.50d.

Validation of the Numerical Model

In order to validate the obtained results, it was necessary to compare the predicted results with published work. Simulation results of this present study were compared with the experimental data of (Hoekstra, 2000), (Zhao, Shen, & Kang, 2004) referenced by (Jafarnejhad, Salarian, Kheradmand, & Khaleghinia, 2021) and the numerical data of (El-Batsh, 2013).

Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively shows the comparison of the pressure drop and separation efficiency variation at different values (5-30 m/s) of gas inlet velocity (with $d_p/d = 0.5$) obtained from the present numerical study with the above-mentioned results. It can be seen that there is a reasonable agreement between them. It can also be observed that a cyclone pressure drop can be strongly influenced by the particle-laden gas inlet velocity as shown in Figure 3 that, increasing the inlet velocity increases the pressure drop through the cyclone. The comparison figure also indicates that for a specific inlet velocity with $d_p/d = 0.5$, the pressure drop obtained from this present study has the lowest value when compared with others tested under the same condition. This is an improvement offered from this design which also confirms the validity of the model. Unlike the pressure drop, it was more difficult to determine the collection efficiency because it is dependent upon particle size distribution of the solid adsorbent incoming particles. A study comparison was performed on the cyclone collection efficiency as a function of its inlet gas velocity by varying the velocity from 10-30m/s based on the available data from the above-mentioned published works with the same test conditions.

Figure 4 shows that for a typical size of the solid adsorbent particle tested, increasing the cyclone inlet velocity would cause a corresponding increase in the cyclone separation capability which can be traced to the increase in the centrifugal force on the solid adsorbent particles.

Figure 3. Comparison between the Experimental Data, Numerical Result and the Present Study

Figure 4. Comparison between the Experimental Data, Numerical Result and the Present Study

This increase trend agrees well with other compared results both experimental and numerical but a sizeable discrepancy is noticed among all these results at low inlet velocities. This might be traceable to the different particle size distributions of the incoming particles considered because it is more difficult to determine the collection efficiency since it is dependent upon particle size distribution of the incoming solid particles.

Results and Discussion

The main parameters that determine the performance of a reverse flow tangential gas-solid cyclone separator are: pressure drop, cut size diameter and the collection or separation efficiency. The simulation results on the effects of the cyclone d_{pe} on these three performance indicators are presented as follows:

Effects of Particle Exit Diameter on the Cyclone Pressure Drop

The pressure drop of a cyclone is an indicator of its energy consumption. For the range of the Co (gas inlet solid loadings) tested which is 5-30 kg solid/kg of gas of 50 – 500 μm particles size range at the gas inlet velocity of 10m/s, as observed from Figure 5, there is a decreasing trend in the pressure drop as the particle exit diameter increases. There is a notable percentage reduction in the pressure drop up till around 0.038m particle exit diameter after which the percentage reduction becomes marginal. It is also worth mentioning from this figure that there is a reduction in the pressure drop with increasing solid loading. This reduction is more significant (about 12.88% reduction) between 5 and 10 kg solid/kg of gas as it is obvious due to the wide margin between them. This reduction trend continues until after 20 kg solid/kg of gas after which the trend is almost marginal. The major explanation for this pressure drop decrease with increasing solid loading is that, when solid adsorbents are fed into the gas stream, there will be a rise in the cyclone wall friction due to the presence of solid adsorbent strands descending along the cyclone wall, which reduces the gas tangential velocity in the cyclone body with the resultant effect of lowering the pressure drop. Furthermore, it is obvious from the marginality trend in Figure 5 that the improvement (reduction) in pressure drop with increasing solid adsorbent particle loading does not continue indefinitely. There is a solid adsorbent particle loading at which the pressure drop reaches a minimum value after which it rises with any further increasing solid adsorbent particle loading. Therefore, for the test conditions in this work, one may then want take

0.038m and 20 kg solid/kg of gas as the optimum particle exit diameter and solid loading.

Figure 5. Effects of Particle Exit Diameter on the Cyclone Pressure Drop for Different Solid Loadings

Effects of Particle Exit Diameter on the Cyclone Cut Size Diameter

The cut size diameter of a cyclone is that size of the particles that will be collected from the gas stream with 50% efficiency. Particles larger than x_{50} will be removed with a greater efficiency and smaller particles with a lower efficiency. With all the solid loadings (5-30 kg solid/kg of gas) of 50 – 500 μm particles size range tested at the gas inlet velocity of 10m/s, there was a direct proportionality between the cut size diameter and the particle exit diameter as shown in Figure 6. Though there was a corresponding increase in the cut size diameter with increasing solid loading but the increment was most significant from 5 - 10 kg solid/kg of gas (about 22.75% increment) and continued though with less % increment until 20 kg solid/kg of gas after which the percentage increment was almost marginal. This again confirms 20 kg solid/kg of gas as the optimum solid loading.

Figure 6. Effects of Particle Exit Diameter on the Cyclone Cut Size Diameter for Different Solid Loadings

Effects of Particle Exit Diameter on the Cyclone Collection Efficiency

The separation characteristics of a cyclone are best described by the so-called grade-efficiency curve (GEC), which is the separation efficiency for a given feed particle size or (narrow) range of particles sizes (Hoffmann & Stein, 2008). The grade efficiency performance of the cyclone was investigated using the optimum particle exit diameter and solid loading with all the other simulation parameters kept constant and this is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Grade Efficiency Performance of the Cyclone

The shape is very much in agreement with those in the literature. Interestingly, there was no observable change in the overall separation

efficiency with increasing particle exit diameter over the range of solid loadings of 50 – 500 μm particles size range at the gas inlet velocity of 10m/s. However, a slight variation was observed with particles sizes below this size range.

Conclusion

The effects of particle exit diameter on the performance criteria namely: pressure drop, cut size diameter and the separation efficiency of a reverse flow tangential gas-solid cyclone separator was numerically investigated with the use of MATLAB software. Activated carbon of 50 – 500 μm particle size range with the gas inlet solid loadings range of 5-30 kg solid/kg of gas at the gas inlet velocity of 10m/s was used for the model. For these test conditions, the simulation results have shown a decreasing trend in the pressure drop and an increasing trend in the cut size diameter with increasing particle exit diameter for all the solid loadings. There was a notable percentage reduction in the pressure drop up till around 0.038m particle exit diameter after which the percentage reduction became marginal. A reduction in the pressure drop and an increase in the cut size diameter with increasing solid loading were also observed with a significant reduction (about 12.88%) and a noticeable increment (about 22.75%) between 5 and 10 kg solid/kg of gas and almost marginal reduction and increment respectively after 20 kg solid/kg of gas. There was no observable change in the overall separation efficiency with increasing particle exit diameter over the tested range of solid loadings but a slight variation was observed with particles sizes below this size range. This study results proved that for the optimum design of a cyclone whose purpose is for product separation and recovery from a high solid particle (product) loaded gases, the design of the product exit has a considerable effect on the pressure drop (energy consumption indicator) and the cut size diameter but less effects on the overall collection efficiency.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the supports provided by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) and the Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham, United Kingdom.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

Nomenclature

A_R The total surface area of the inside of the cyclone contributing to the frictional drag, (m^2)

c_o Incoming solid loading/ loading ratio in cyclone inlet, (kg/kg)

c_{o_2} Incoming solid loading/ loading ratio in cyclone inlet, (kg/m^3)

c_{oL} Limiting loading

g acceleration due to gravity, (m^2/s)

\dot{M}_{sc} Mass flow rate of adsorbent, (kg/s)

m_{sf} Mass of solid fed into the cyclone, (kg)

m_g Mass of circulating gas entering into the cyclone, (kg)

m_c Mass of solid adsorbent collected, (kg)

m Slope of grade efficiency curve

n Number of size fraction

\dot{Q} Gas (particle laden) volumetric flow rate, (m^3/s)

r Cyclone radius, (m)

r_v Radius of vortex finder, (m)

r_{cm} Mean cyclone radius, (m)

r_{in} Radial position of the center of cyclone/mean inlet radius, (m)

Re_p Particle Reynolds number

R Universal gas constant, ($J/(mole.K)$)

u_{t50} Terminal (radial) velocity of x_{50} in the inner vortex, (m/s)

u_x Tangential velocity of the conveying gas at the inner core (vortex) radius (at r_v), (m/s)

u_c Tangential velocity in the vicinity of (near) the cyclone wall (at r), (m/s)

\bar{u}_{sc} Speed of adsorbent flow, (m/s)

u Velocity component in x direction, (m/s)

v_i Mean gas inlet velocity, (m/s)

v_m Mean (wall) axial velocity, (m/s)

v_x Mean axial velocity in the vortex finder, (m/s)

W_i i th mass fraction of the total mass of adsorbent feed

x_{50} Cut point diameter (diameter of particle which has 50% probability of capture from the inner vortex), (m)

x Axial coordinate, (m)

x_i i th particle diameter, (m)

z Axial coordinate, (m)

Greek symbols

f Total friction coefficient including the reaction of the solid phase to the gas flow

f_{sw} Gas friction factor for smooth cyclone wall

f_{rw} Gas friction factor for rough cyclone wall

α Entrance constriction coefficient

ϵ Absolute roughness of the inside surface of the cyclone wall, (m)

ε Adsorbent porosity

μ_g Gas dynamic viscosity, (Pa s)

ρ_g Gas density, (kg/m^3)

ρ_p Adsorbent particle density, (kg/m^3)

ρ_z Adsorbent density, kg/m^3

η_t Overall separation/Collection efficiency (%)

η_i Collection efficiency of the average particle size of i th fraction (%)
 τ_R Gas residence time, (s)

References

- El-Batsh, H. M. (2013). Improving cyclone performance by proper selection of the exit pipe. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 37(7), 5286–5303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2012.10.044>
- Elsayed, K., & Lacor, C. (2010). Optimization of the cyclone separator geometry for minimum pressure drop using mathematical models and CFD simulations. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 65(22), 6048–6058. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2010.08.042>
- Fassani, F. L., & Goldstein, L. (2000). A study of the effect of high inlet solids loading on a cyclone separator pressure drop and collection efficiency. *Powder Technology*, 107(1), 60–65. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910\(99\)00091-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910(99)00091-1)
- Gil, A., Romeo, L. M., & Cortes, C. (2002). Effect of the solid loading on a pressurized fluidized bed combustor's cyclone with pneumatic extraction of solids. *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, 25(4), 407–415. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-4125\(200204\)25:4<407::AID-CEAT407>3.0.CO;2-4](https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-4125(200204)25:4<407::AID-CEAT407>3.0.CO;2-4)
- Grace, J. R., Avidan, A. A., & Knowlton, T. M. (Eds.). (1997). *Circulating fluidized beds* (1st ed.). Blackie Academic & Professional.
- Hoekstra, A. J. (2000). *Gas flow field and collection efficiency of cyclone separators* (Ph.D. thesis). Technical University Delft.
- Hoffmann, A. C., & Stein, L. E. (2008). *Gas Cyclones and Swirl Tubes: Principles, Design and Operation* (2nd ed.). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-74787-9>
- Hoffmann, A. C., van Santen, A., Allen, R. W. K., & Clift, R. (1992). Effects of geometry and solid loading on the performance of gas cyclones. *Powder Technology*, 70(1), 83–91. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(92\)85058-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(92)85058-4)
- Huang, A.-N., Ito, K., Fukasawa, T., Fukui, K., & Kuo, H.-P. (2018). Effects of particle mass loading on the hydrodynamics and separation efficiency of a cyclone separator. *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers*, 90, 61–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2017.12.016>
- Jafarnezhad, A., Salarian, H., Kheradmand, S., & Khaleghinia, J. (2021). Performance improvement of a cyclone separator using different shapes of vortex finder under high-temperature operating condition. *Journal of the Brazilian Society of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering*, 43(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40430-020-02783-8>
- Morin, M., Raynal, L., Karri, S. B. R., & Cocco, R. (2021). Effect of solid loading and inlet aspect ratio on cyclone efficiency and pressure drop: Experimental study and CFD simulations. *Powder Technology*, 377, 174–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2020.08.052>
- Muschelknautz, E., & Greif, V. (1993). Fundamentals and practical aspects of cyclones. In A. A. Avidan (Ed.), *Circulating Fluidized Bed Technology IV: Proc. 4th Int. Conf. Circulating Fluidized Beds, Somerset/Pa., USA* (pp. 20–27).
- Muschelknautz, E., & Krambrock, W. (1970). Aerodynamische Beiwerte des Zyklonabscheiders aufgrund neuer und verbesserter Messungen. *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, 42(5), 247–255. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cite.330420503>
- Muschelknautz, U. (2019). Design and calculation methods for uniflow cyclones. *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, 42(3), 52–63. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.201900040>
- Scheid, C. M., & Massarani, G. (1992). XX Encontro Sobre Escoamento em Meios Porosos (ENEMP). *UFSCar* (10 pp.).
- Sommerfeld, M., & Taborda, M. A. (2024). Understanding solid particle transport in a gas cyclone separator. *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*, 181, 104992. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2024.104992>
- Stairmand, C. J. (1949). Pressure drop in cyclone separators. *Engineering*, 168(B), 409–412.

Tardin Jr., P. R., & Goldstein Jr., L. (1994). Anais do III Congresso de Engenharia Mecânica Norte-Nordeste-Belem-PA, Brasil (pp. 179–183).

Tawari, T. D., & Zenz, F. A. (1984). Evaluating cyclone efficiencies from stream compositions. *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, *91*(9), 69–73.

Trefz, M., & Muschelknautz, E. (1993). Extended cyclone theory for gas flows with high solids concentrations. *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, *16*(3), 153–160. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.270160303>

Tuzla, K., & Chen, J. (1992). Performance of a cyclone under high solid loadings.

Yao, Y., Shang, M., Ke, X., Huang, Z., Zhou, T., & Lyu, J. (2024). Effects of the inlet particle spatial distribution on the performance of a gas-solid cyclone separator. *Particuology*, *85*, 133–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2023.03.024>

Zenz, F. A. (1975). *Manual on disposal of refinery wastes: Volume on atmospheric emissions*. API Publication.

Zhao, B., Shen, H., & Kang, Y. (2004). Development of a symmetrical spiral inlet to improve cyclone separator performance. *Powder Technology*, *145*(1), 47–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2004.06.001>